

THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISING ACTIVITIES ON INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A MEDICAL INSTITUTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655249>

Abstract

The article considers approaches to improving the organization of advertising activities in medical institutions to increase their competitiveness. Nine stages were formed and revealed, which should be applied by medical institutions to increase their level of competitiveness, namely: market research; brand development; creation of a website and presence in social networks; targeted advertising; reviews and reputation; staff training and development; partnerships and networking; analysis of marketing and advertising results; compliance with laws and regulations.

Keywords: advertising, competitiveness, brand, marketing, website development, healthcare.

Introduction. The formation of advertising activity has undergone a complex historical development process. At the current stage of the development of society, advertising occupies one of the most influential places and is the subject of study by specialists of various sciences. Scientific research and methods of psychology, sociology, mathematics, economics, and statistics are used to build advertising strategies. The main place in the study of advertising belongs to marketing. Advertising affects various aspects of human life, including the development of social relations and modern public opinion, increasing the quality of life. Nowadays, advertising of medical drugs, medical services, medical equipment, etc. is a very common phenomenon. This advertisement is distributed mainly through mass media (television and radio channels, printed mass media, the Internet). High-quality medical advertising has a positive effect on the process of providing medical services, raises the level of public awareness of the medical institution and its services, and supports fair competition in society. The functioning of fair competition is based on the formation of quality regulatory acts in the field of advertising and their compliance, which remains the subject of study by domestic and international legislators.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A number of works by scientists in the field of law and those engaged in medical practice are devoted to the issue of public health protection and advertising activities in the field of health care institutions. The development of effective and timely approaches to the advertising activities of health care institutions (hereinafter referred to as HCI) are of great importance, requiring further in-depth research. Among the scientists who studied the issue of the organization of advertising activities of HCI are: G. Armstrong, M. Bilynska, R.

Jones, K. Keller, P. Kotler, O. Nebylytsia, YU. Voronenko, K. Zhyrnova and other.

The purpose of the article is to develop practical recommendations for improving and generalizing approaches to the organization of advertising activities of a medical institution to increase its competitiveness.

Research results. Management of increasing the competitiveness of a medical institution under the influence of advertising is an important aspect in the conditions of the modern market economy for its successful development. Nine stages that medical institutions should apply to increase their level of competitiveness have been formulated and listed below.

1. *Market research.* The first step is to analyze the medical services market in the selected region. Identification of competitors, their strengths and weaknesses, as well as requests and needs of the target audience of the medical institution.

2. *Brand development.* Creating a strong brand of a medical institution that reflects its values, quality of services and unique features. Effective brand management will help the institution stand out from the competition.

3. *Creation of a website and presence in social networks.* Development of an informative and user-friendly website that will feature services, patient reviews, feedback and contact information. Active use of social networks to communicate with patients and publish useful information.

4. *Targeted advertising.* Determining the target audience and using targeted advertising on the Internet to reveal the necessary information to patients. This may include contextual advertising, social media advertising and search engine optimization.

5. *Feedback and reputation.* Paying attention to reputation management. Encouraging patients to leave

positive feedback about the medical facility and actively responding to negative feedback, actively solving emerging problems.

6. *Training and development of personnel.* Education of medical and administrative staff at relevant trainings and courses to master the latest trends and advanced methods of medicine and patient care at a high level. Quality service and a personal approach can become a powerful competitive advantage.

7. *Partnerships and networking.* Give preference to opportunities for cooperation with other medical institutions and organizations in the selected region and beyond. This can help to expand the client base of the medical institution and improve the level of services.

8. *Analysis of marketing and advertising results.* Regular evaluation of the results of marketing and advertising efforts. Measuring the effectiveness of various advertising companies and making adjustments to the strategy based on the received data.

9. *Compliance with laws and regulations.* Mandatory compliance with all laws and regulatory measures related to advertising in the medical field.

Managing the competitiveness of a medical institution through advertising requires a systematic and long-term approach. The key factors for the success of a medical facility will be the quality of services and effective brand and marketing management. The nine main strategies (directions) of managing the improvement of the competitiveness of the medical institution have been identified in more detail and gradually revealed for implementation in the practical activities of the medical institution. Each of the nine listed strategies (stages) can be achieved by completing a set of tasks that will ensure the implementation of the corresponding strategy.

I. Market research.

Conducting an analysis of the medical services market in the selected region will allow you to better understand the current situation, competition and to consider potential opportunities for the medical institution. The analysis can be based on the following stages.

1. *Collection of data on the medical services market.* At the initial stage, the geographical boundaries of the studied region should be determined. Information should be collected on existing health facilities in the area, including hospitals, clinics, private practices, and other health care organizations. Conduct research on the specialization and services of each medical facility in the region.

2. *Analysis of competitors.* The assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of competitors is carried out through the study of their reputational component, issues of pricing and quality of the offered services, marketing strategies. By studying ratings and reviews of competitors on online platforms and social networks.

3. *Definition of the target audience.* Establishing who is the target audience that will use the services of the medical institution. When establishing a target audience, you can take into account such characteristics as a certain age group, gender, geographic location, medical needs, etc. Conducting a study of the needs and preferences of the selected target audience.

4. *Analysis of supply and demand.* It involves an assessment of the volume of demand for medical services in the studied region. It may include analysis of statistical data on morbidity and demographics for a specified period, as well as the current supply of health services and identify open positions of health services.

5. *Research of legislation and regulation of the medical field.* Thorough study of regulatory and legislative acts in the medical field, which are in force in the studied region, especially those related to the chosen direction of providing medical services. They can influence the conditions for the provision of medical services and, accordingly, the formation of an advertising strategy.

6. *Analysis of trends and changes in health care.* Study of current trends and changes in the field of health care, such as the introduction of new technologies, changes in insurance, etc.

7. *SWOT analysis.* Carrying out a SWOT analysis of a medical institution based on the developed results of the market analysis. Identification of strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats.

8. *Strategy formation.* Based on the received data, develop a strategy that will help the medical institution stand out in the market, attract the target audience and develop effectively.

9. *Regular updating of data.* Note that the market for medical services can change over time, so it is important to regularly update data and analyze changes in the market.

Analysis of the medical services market will allow managers to better understand the place that a medical institution occupies or will occupy in the market, determine strategic directions of development and make informed decisions to increase its competitiveness.

II. Brand development.

Building a strong brand for a medical facility is an important step in managing its competitiveness and attracting patients. An effective brand should reflect the core values, quality of services and unique features of a medical institution. In order to create and strengthen the brand of a medical institution, it is necessary to carry out the specified measures.

1. *Definition of brand values.* The definition of the main values and principles of a medical institution should be based on answers to questions. What makes a medical institution special? What principles are the basis of medical practice in this institution (in a general sense)? For example, it can be high quality of service, increased attention and care for patients, implementation of advanced technologies, etc.

2. *Determining the needs of the target audience for brand development.* Determine which groups of patients will be involved. Studying their needs, preferences and expectations from the medical service to take into account when developing the brand.

3. *Development of a unique offer.* Creation of a unique selling proposition (Unique Selling Proposition, USP), which will help distinguish a medical institution from competitors. This can be something that distinguishes the institution from other medical institutions (for example, specialization in a certain field of medicine, the work of highly qualified doctors with a world

name, performing extremely complex surgical interventions, exclusive technologies and treatment methods, a personalized approach to patients, etc.).

4. *Name and logo.* Choosing an appropriate name for a medical facility that will be easy to remember and reflect the nature of its activities. Development of a logo that will visually correspond to the brand identity of the medical institution.

5. *Design and atmosphere.* Creating a pleasant and professional atmosphere in a medical institution. Including interior design, color scheme, furniture and other details that will correspond to the brand identity of the medical institution.

6. *Creating an online presence with brand features.* It consists in the development of an informative and functional website that will display medical services, a team of doctors, patient reviews and contact information, which will be associated with brand features (logo, color scheme, etc.). Brand promotion through active participation in social networks and maintaining relevant profiles. This will allow interaction with patients and spread information about the medical facility.

7. *Marketing and advertising.* Development of a marketing strategy, in which the brand values and USP of the medical institution will be respected. Simultaneous use of various marketing channels, such as advertising on the Internet, social networks, content marketing and various activities to actively promote the brand of the medical institution.

8. *Creation of educational content for specialists and patients.* Conferences can be held on the basis of a medical institution, advanced treatment practices can be implemented with the participation of specialists from various medical institutions. It is also important to develop content that will help patients understand and appreciate the expertise of a medical facility. It can be a blog with useful articles, tips on leading a healthy lifestyle, webinars, video lessons.

9. *Reputation management.* On an ongoing basis, monitoring of compliance with reputational aspects of the clinic. Prompt response to patient feedback and resolution of emerging issues.

10. *Measuring and adjusting brand strategy.* Systematic measurement of the effectiveness of the brand strategy and making the necessary adjustments based on the received data.

Formation and constant support of a brand is a process that requires a lot of time and effort, but it can significantly increase the competitiveness of a medical institution and will contribute to attracting more patients.

III. *Creation of a website and presence in social networks.*

Nowadays, designing a website for a medical facility plays an important role in establishing an online presence, providing information to patients and attracting new customers. The steps that will help you develop an effective website are as follows.

1. *Defining the goals of the site.* Determine what goals the medical facility needs to achieve with the website. For example, it can be providing information about medical services, making an online appointment, creating a client's personal account, sending test results

to the client's account, increasing the number of requests for consultations with a doctor, etc.

2. *Analysis of audience needs.* Study of the needs and expectations of the target audience of the medical institution. Figuring out which informational and functional elements would be most useful to them.

3. *Choosing a domain name.* Choosing a domain name that is easy to remember and reflects the brand of the medical institution for this website.

4. *Choice of hosting and platform.* Choosing a hosting provider and platform for creating a website. Popular platforms for medical institutions are WordPress, Joomla, Drupal and others.

5. *Development of information architecture.* Defining the structure of the website, including sections, pages and menus. Providing easy navigation and quick access to important information.

6. *Design and visual design of the website.* Development of a site design that corresponds to the brand identity of a medical institution. Paying attention to the color scheme, fonts, logo, images, interactive elements, video backgrounds, etc.

7. *Content creation.* Writing informative texts about the medical institution, medical services, team of doctors and other key aspects. Add a feature - frequently asked questions (FAQ) and a blog with useful articles.

8. *Integration of online recording.* Development of a functional and simple online appointment with a doctor. Providing a convenient booking and notification process.

9. *Optimization for search engines (SEO).* Optimize the site for search engines so that it is easily found in search results. Enable keywords and meta tags.

10. *Mobile adaptation.* Work on making the website of the medical institution fully adapted to mobile devices, as more and more users access the Internet through smartphones and tablets.

11. *Security and Privacy.* Ensuring a high level of security and protection of patient data on the institution's website.

12. *Testing and Debugging.* Conducting site testing to ensure the correctness of its operation and the absence of errors at the beginning of work and during current operation.

13. *Launch and Promotion.* After successful testing, the site is launched and its promotion begins with the help of marketing campaigns and social networks.

14. *Updates and Support.* It is necessary to regularly update the content on the site and monitor its relevance. Provide up-to-date information about the work schedule, services, price policy and contacts of the medical institution.

Creating a website for a medical facility is a long-term investment that will help attract new users of medical services and maintain contact with regular customers by providing them with access to important information. Also, the website of a medical institution is its face, it can provide a lot of information to other users (representatives of local self-government, third-party medical specialists, public organizations, various services, etc.), so the information posted on it should be approached very carefully.

IV. Targeted advertising.

Targeted advertising about a healthcare facility can help attract patients in urgent medical situations that will match their profile and increase awareness of the healthcare facility. Key strategies for targeted advertising of a medical facility are given.

1. *Geotargeting.* "Geotargeting, - in part. Geographic targeting. In web development and internet marketing, a method of delivering content to a visitor that matches their geographic location; regional binding allows the site to rebuild content for different regions" [1]. Setting up an ad campaign with geotargeting is all about reaching people in specific geographic areas. This is especially useful for attracting patients near the hospital.

2. *Search advertising.* Using contextual advertising in search engines, such as Google AdWords, so that the medical facility is visible in the search results for queries related to emergency medical care. For example, keywords might include "hospital near," "dentistry," "teeth whitening," "endodontic treatment," "esthetic restoration," "veneers," "crowns," "dental surgery," "implantation," "dental prostheses", "children's dentistry", "bite correction", etc.

3. *Social networks.* Conducting an advertising campaign on social networks such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, taking into account the geography and interests of the target audience. Use images and text that emphasize the importance of dental care (services).

4. *Retargeting.* "Retargeting (eng. retargeting) is an Internet marketing tool that allows you to show ads to specific users who have already interacted with your site or other advertising materials. This can be visiting the site pages, watching a video, registering on the site or adding a product to the cart" [2]. Using retargeting to retarget patients who have already visited the hospital's website or expressed interest in its services with more specific messages about dental services.

5. *Mobile advertising.* As more people search for health care information from mobile devices, consider mobile advertising, such as mobile app ads and mobile search ads.

6. *Relevance and clarity.* Be sure to provide clear information on how to contact the dental clinic, including a phone number, address, and location map. Pay constant attention to the relevance of data.

7. *Reviews and ratings.* If the hospital has positive reviews and a high rating, you should share them in promotional messages. This will help to increase the confidence of patients.

8. *Promotions and special offers.* Provide information about any promotions or special offers for patients who have applied to the hospital.

9. *Monitoring and optimization.* Regularly monitor and optimize advertising campaigns based on performance data. This will help maximize results and optimize the budget.

Targeted advertising for a hospital, according to its profile, should be aimed at providing important information and assistance in situations where every minute counts.

V. Feedback and Reputation.

Encouraging patients to leave positive reviews about a medical institution can significantly increase its reputation and attract new patients. The following methods and strategies should be used.

1. *Providing high quality services.* This is the most important aspect of the activity of a medical institution. A health care facility must provide high-quality medical care and patient care. The quality of services will be the main factor in receiving positive reviews.

2. *Professional communication.* It is necessary to ensure professional and polite communication with patients at all stages of service, starting with an appointment and ending with consultations, medical services (manipulations).

3. *Active feedback collection.* Encourage patients to leave feedback about their experience at the medical facility. This can be done either verbally or via e-mails or SMS after the visit. Facilitate the process of leaving reviews.

4. *Rewards and bonuses.* Consider giving small rewards or bonuses (for example, a discount on the next appointment) to patients who leave positive reviews about the medical facility.

5. *Participation in online platforms.* Register on online platforms for ratings and reviews in the medical field, such as Google My Business, Yelp, Zocdoc, etc. This will make it easier for patients to leave reviews.

6. *Create an accessible website for reviews.* Provide a section on the medical facility's website where patients can leave reviews. Simplify the process of leaving reviews.

7. *Feedback and response.* Respond to both positive and negative feedback. Thank patients for positive feedback and offer solutions to improve the experience for those who leave negative feedback.

8. *Transparency and honesty.* The staff of the institution must provide truthful information about the services provided by the medical institution. Do not manipulate patient reviews or write bogus reviews.

9. *Staff training.* Train medical and administrative staff to serve patients at a high level. Create a system for evaluating the work of the hospital staff by leaving feedback.

10. *Monitoring and analysis of feedback.* Systematically analyze feedback to identify common trends and improve hospital weaknesses.

11. *Creation of video reviews.* Encourage patients to record video reviews about their experience and treatment outcome. These videos can be a powerful persuasive tool.

12. *Social networks.* Actively use social media to post patient testimonials and success stories.

Be honest and professional when collecting feedback. Work with different types of reviews to ultimately create a positive reputation for the medical facility.

VI. Training and development of personnel.

The training of medical and administrative staff in a HCI is critical to ensuring a high standard of medical care and improving the quality of patient care and the efficient functioning of the facility. This is one of the

key aspects that affects the reputation of a medical institution and is a reliable advertisement. Organization of training for medical and administrative staff of the hospital may include the following stages.

1. *Evaluation of training and development of the plan.* Identification of current training needs among medical and administrative staff of the hospital. This may include consideration of professional accreditation requirements, new technologies or changes in legislation. Development of a training plan taking into account these needs.

2. *Development of individual study plans.* Creation of individual training plans for employees based on their needs and professional goals. Taking into account the specialization of each employee.

3. *Selection of educational programs and resources.* Selection of appropriate training programs and resources that meet learning objectives. These can be courses, seminars, online learning platforms, specialized literature or on-the-job training.

4. *Updating training programs.* Continuous updating of training programs in accordance with changes in medical practice, legislation and technology.

5. *Creation of educational materials.* Preparation of educational materials that will be available to employees for independent study or as part of training programs. These can be textbooks, video lessons, presentations, etc.

6. *On-the-job training.* Providing on-the-job training and internships for employees so that employees can apply their knowledge and skills in practice. Practical training and internship is an important element of training that consolidates theoretical knowledge.

7. *Professional instructors and trainers.* If necessary, professional instructors or trainers who specialize in medical and administrative issues can be invited. They can train employees and practice the acquired skills with them.

8. *Creating a learning culture.* Encouraging employees for continuous training and self-development. Creating an atmosphere in the institution in which learning is valued and supported.

9. *Certification and accreditation.* Supporting employees in obtaining the necessary certifications and accreditations in accordance with their specialization and the requirements of legislation in the medical field.

10. *Ethics training and patient care.* Staff training in ethics and patient care skills includes issues of confidentiality, polite communication, and a patient-centered approach.

11. *Tracking the latest trends.* Tracking the latest medical trends and innovations in the field of health care and their integration into the training of the staff of a medical institution.

12. *Technology training.* Staff training to use modern medical technologies and information support systems.

13. *Financial support.* Providing employees with access to financial support and opportunities to obtain additional educational degrees or courses.

14. *Assessment of success and feedback.* Evaluating the effectiveness of training through regular reviews, analyzing employee progress and providing

feedback. This may include testing, practical assignments or professional assessments. Using assessment results to improve training programs.

Continuous professional training and development will help the medical staff of the institution to improve the quality of medical care, increase the level of trust of patients and strengthen the reputation of the hospital. This is a reliable investment in the future development of the health care organization.

VII. Partnerships and networking.

Cooperation with other medical institutions and organizations can be useful for expanding the client base of a medical institution. This can help improve the availability and variety of medical services, as well as strengthen the institution's position in the market. The methods of cooperation between partners and their interaction are indicated below.

1. *Referral programs.* Mutually beneficial referral relationships with other medical institutions (hospitals, clinics or specialized centers) are established. This may include referring patients for consultations or treatment at the clinic and vice versa.

2. *Shared medical services.* Consideration of the possibility of providing joint medical services with other institutions. For example, a medical facility may partner with a laboratory or educational center to provide additional services to patients.

3. *Participation in health care networks.* Join medical networks or associations that unite different medical institutions. This can help establish contacts and gain access to a larger customer base.

4. *Exchange of knowledge and experience.* Conducting seminars, webinars or training programs jointly with other medical institutions to share knowledge and experience. This will attract the attention and respect of medical professionals and patients.

5. *Joint advertising and marketing.* Creation of a joint advertising campaign and marketing initiative to increase the visibility of the medical institution and partner institutions and the information field.

6. *Telemedical consultations.* Development of a telemedicine consultation program with other institutions to ensure access to medical care for patients in remote areas.

7. *Sharing of resources.* Consideration of the possibility of sharing equipment and infrastructure with other institutions to optimize costs.

8. *Exchange of medical data.* Establishing a system of exchange of medical information with other institutions, adhering to data confidentiality standards.

9. *Cooperation with insurance companies.* Organization of cooperation with local insurance companies, which can improve the access of patients to the services of a medical institution.

10. *Network growth.* Consideration of the possibility of expanding the medical facility through a merger, acquisition or creation of new units.

It is important to ensure transparency and clarity in all healthcare facility partnerships and create agreements to define responsibilities and expectations for collaboration. Cooperation with other medical institu-

tions can significantly improve the quality and availability of medical care in the region and contribute to the growth of the client base.

VIII. Analysis of marketing and advertising results.

Evaluation of the results of marketing and advertising activities of a medical institution plays an important role in understanding the effectiveness of the efforts made in the development of HCI and allows making adjustments to the strategy, if necessary. There are ten steps for evaluating the results of marketing and advertising activities of a medical institution.

1. Establishing specific indicators of success. Outline in advance what specific indicators the medical institution will use to evaluate the results. These can be indicators such as the number of new patients, website conversion rate, ROI, brand awareness, and others.

2. Traffic analysis and website analytics. Using analytics tools (for example, Google Analytics) to track website traffic. Estimating how many visitors come through advertising campaigns, what pages they visit and what the conversion rate is.

3. Tracking traffic sources. Assess which marketing channels and advertising platforms bring the most traffic and conversions. This can help determine where to increase the budget and improve the strategy.

4. Patient surveys and feedback. Conducting a survey among patients of a medical institution to determine how they learned about the hospital and how they evaluate its marketing activities. This will help facility managers understand what is working and what can be improved.

5. Tracking of calls and requests. If the medical facility has a telephone consultation line or online inquiry forms, tracking them will allow you to know how many inquiries are received from potential patients through marketing and advertising campaigns.

6. Monitoring of social networks. Assessment of the activity and engagement of social media publications of a medical institution. Comparison of metrics such as number of likes, comments, reposts and new followers.

7. Comparison with competitors. Research of marketing strategies used by competitors of a medical facility and evaluation of their performance. This will make it possible to better assess the position of the medical institution in the market of medical services.

8. Financial assessment. Analysis of the financial results of the hospital's marketing campaigns. Conducting cost-benefit analysis of healthcare services provided to determine which campaigns bring the most revenue and which can be optimized.

9. Periodic reviews and correction of the strategy. Periodic review of the results of the implemented strategy and their analysis. Making, if necessary, corrections to the marketing strategy based on the received data to improve the efficiency of the medical institution.

10. Consultations with professionals. If necessary, you should seek help from marketing consultants or agencies to evaluate and improve the marketing strategy of the medical institution.

IX. Compliance with laws and regulations.

Evaluation of the results of marketing and advertising activities should be a continuous process that will help make informed decisions and achieve the goals of the medical institution. Compliance with the legislation on advertising in the medical field is an important aspect that will help protect medical institutions from legal problems and ensure ethical and honest advertising of medical services. It is important to master and comply with the law at the state and local levels. Ten basic principles that should be followed in marketing and advertising activities are highlighted.

1. Honesty and accuracy. Advertising of medical services must be honest and accurate. You may not post false or fraudulent information about the services provided or the results of treatment.

2. Privacy and Consent. Confidentiality of patient information should be maintained and their consent obtained for the use of their data in promotional materials, if necessary.

3. Licenses and accreditations. It is necessary to be sure that the medical facility has all the necessary licenses and accreditations, which may be indicated in the advertisement, if required by law.

4. Photos and images. When using photos of patients or treatment results, permission must be obtained to ensure that they truly reflect the real experience.

5. Compliance with medical standards. Advertising must comply with medical standards and best practices established by the medical community.

6. Price announcements. When posting information about prices for medical services, you must be sure that this information is honest and understandable.

Figure 1. Stages of increasing the competitiveness of a medical institution

Source: Developed by the authors.

7. Avoidance of false patient recruitment methods.

The use of manipulative methods to attract patients (for example, creating non-existent expiration dates for offers for medical services) should be avoided.

8. Control of the content of third-party agencies.

When using third-party advertising agencies, you should check that they also comply with advertising laws and medical ethics.

9. Transparency and feedback. Providing additional information and feedback at the request of patients and regulatory authorities.

10. Staff training. Organization of training of medical and administrative personnel in regulations and rules of advertising in the medical field.

It is important not only to comply with the law, but also to maintain high ethical standards in medical advertising in order to build trust with patients and strengthen the reputation of the medical institution. All the above-mentioned and disclosed stages of increasing the competitiveness of a medical institution are grouped and shown in Figure 1.

The above-mentioned main stages will contribute to increasing the level of competitiveness of a medical institution that can perform all the proposed stages step by step. Each health care institution can also selectively use in its activity exactly that stage to improve the development of competitiveness, which, in the opinion of its managers, needs to be pumped in the first place.

Conclusions. Management of increasing the competitiveness of a medical institution under the influence of advertising activities should be carried out using the following stages: market research; brand development; creation of a website and presence in social networks; targeted advertising; reviews and reputation; staff training and development; partnerships and networking;

analysis of marketing and advertising results; compliance with laws and regulations. All the indicated stages consist of more detailed steps that are disclosed. A comprehensive model of increasing the competitiveness of medical institutions is summarized and proposed.

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